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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MULTIPURPOSE HERBAL SHAMPOO

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ABSTRACT

Herbal Shampoo is a cosmetic preparation which uses herbs and it is meant for washing of hair and scalp just like a regular shampoo. Shampoos are the products which remove surface grease, dust from the hair shaft. The herbal shampoo was formulated with natural ingredients like *Emblica officinalis Gaerth* (Amla), *Azadirachta indica* (Neem), *Acacia Arabica* (Shikakai), *Spindus mukorossi* (Reetha), *Murrayakoenigii* (Curry leaves), *Ecliptaalba* (Bhringraj), *Aloe barbadensis miller* (Aloe). The formulation at laboratory scale was done and evaluated for number of parameters to ensure its safety and efficacy. Three formulations were prepared i.e. F1, F2 and F3 and the evaluation parameters were studied like Foam stability, pH test, Detergency and cleansing action, Physical appearance, etc. Formulation F3 was showing good pH, good detergency and cleansing action, good physical appearance as compared to other formulations.

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INTRODUCTION

Hair is one of the external barometers of internal body conditions. It is a crucial component of the human body.^[1] Produced from ectoderm and serve as the body's protecting appendages.^[2] It is connected to sweat and sebaceous glands. Products for hair care are preparations designed to cleanse, alter the texture, change the color, nourish the hair and give the hair a healthy appearance.^[3] Shampoo is defined as a cosmetic product used to remove build up of sebum, dirt from the scalp and residue from hair grooming products.^[4,5] Similar to ordinary shampoo, herbal shampoo is a cosmetic preparation made from herbs derived from plants and it is used to wash hair and scalp. It serves as a substitute for the commercially available synthetic shampoo.^[6,7] Due to the minimal side effects and lower cost of herbal products the community became drawn to the mas opposed to synthetic shampoo which has detrimental effects on skin, hair and eyes.

The current study's goal is to create and assess a multipurpose herbal shampoo by removing all conventionally added synthetic components and using a variety of herbs. This shampoo strengthens, darkens and encourages hair growth while getting rid of dandruff, sebum and impurities. Additionally, it serves as a conditioning agent. All of these functions are carried out by this herbal shampoo powder without harming or compromising hair.^[1]

Shampoo is a hair care product that we use on a daily basis to clean our hair and scalp. Shampoos are a viscous solution of detergents with appropriate additions, preservatives and active substances that are mostly used as beautifying agents. Typically, it is massaged into damp hair after application and then washed with water. Synthetic surfactants are included to synthetic shampoos primarily for their washing and foaming qualities; nevertheless, frequent use of these surfactants can cause major side effects such dryness in the hair, irritation of the scalp and eyes and hair loss.^[8] Herbal formulations are thought to be a good substitute for synthetic shampoo, but making cosmetics with just natural ingredients is a challenging undertaking.^[9] Numerous medicinal plants are popularly employed in shampoo composition because of their purportedly therapeutic benefits on hair.^[10] Shampoos are a viscous mixture of detergents with appropriate additions, preservatives and active chemicals that are mostly used as beautifying agents.^[11]

Fig.No.1:-Herbalsampoo.

Definition of Herbal Shampoo:-

Shampoos are most likely used for cosmetic purposes. It is a hair care product that we use on a daily basis to clean our hair and scalp. Shampoos are sticky detergent solutions with appropriate additions, preservatives and active ingredients that are most commonly used as beautifying agents. It's typically rubbed into damp hair, massaged in and then washed out with a water rinse. The goal of utilizing herbal shampoo is to get rid of makeup – causing debris from hair without removing a lot of sebum. There are a lot of artificial shampoos on the market right now, both medicated and non-medicated. But, natural shampoos have gained popularity since they are safe, enhance customer demand and have no negative side effects.^[12] Herbal shampoo is described as a formulation of a surfactant (surface active material) in an appropriate liquid, solid, or power form that, when applied as directed, will remove skin debris, grease and filth from the hair shaft and scalp without having a negative impact on the user's hair, scalp, or health. There are a plethora of sorts in herbal shampoo are aerosol, powder, liquid, lotion, cream, jelly and specific Herbal Shampoo (Baby, Two Layers, Conditioning and Anti- Dandruff). However, herbal shampoo is likely to be Herbal shampoo's future. It has abotanical extract in addition to all natural components. It aids in hairs adapting to changes in moisture, sheen, growth, thickness and root strength.^[13]

Human Hair:-

Hair is a simple structure that are made up of protein filament is called keratin. Hair is act as barrier for foreign particles like micro organisms and sunlight. Hair is important part for appearance and gender identification. Hair made by two different structure hair follicle and hair shaft. Hair follicles are present below the skin and hair shafts are present above the skin. Before the growth of hair, hair follicles are created. Cell are remained fully hydrated that is keratinized. Sebaceous glands secret oil substance that is sebum.

There are three layer of hair shaftcuticle, cortex, medulla.

Cuticle- It is outer layer of hair. It is made up of six to eleven layer of overlapping with semi- transparent keratin scales.

Cortex – It is middle layer of hair. It gives flexibility and tensile strength to hair. Provide constant melanin granules to the hair. Melanin provides color to hair. It is made up of fibre of keratin which are parallel to the each other.

Medulla – It is the inner most layer of a hair. It has honey comb keratin structure with airspace inside.

Dandruff:-

The most common cosmetic issue and source of public concern in both industrialized and developing nations is dandruff.^[14] The words “tan,” which means “tetter,” and “drof,” which means “dirty,” combine to form the word “dandruff.”^[15] Chronic dandruff on the scalp causes it to peel, itch, and become red because it sheds skin cells. Scalp sheds dead cells almost unnoticeable most of the time, but occasionally it leaves behind noticeable flakes known as dandruff.^[16]

There are two types of dandruff dry dandruff and oily dandruff.**Dry Dandruff-**

It is also known as pityriasis simplex, and it is characterized by an excessive amount of microscopic scales that grow and pile on the scalp. This kind of dandruff doesn't cause a lot of hair loss. There is no sign of skin irritation. The middle of the head is where the scales initially appear, and they later extend to the frontal, parietal, and occipital regions.

Oily dandruff-

Another name for it is Pityriasis Steatoides. It comes onto the scalp when sebum is produced. After puberty, young men are the majority who have it. On the scalp, greasy, dirty-yellow scales appeared accompanied with varying degrees of inflammation. This disorder is most usually associated with hair loss. This kind of dandruff most commonly affects the scalp, armpits, above the breast bone, and behind the ears.^[17]

Cause of Dandruff-

The fungus *Pityrosporum ovale* (P. Ovale), which is naturally found on the scalp and other areas of the skin, can be the source of dandruff. This fungus doesn't usually cause any harm. However, the scalp will create more oil due to hormonal changes, stress and weather changes, which will lead to the fungus P. Ovale multiplying. As the fungus becomes larger, the itching of the skin cells on the scalp, hair follicle loss and what is known as “dandruff.” The precise process that causes dandruff is the production of lipases, which are enzymes. These enzymes are used by the fungus *Malassezia* to convert sebum into oleic acid. When oleic acid reaches the epidermis, it increases skin cell turnover in those who are vulnerable.^[18]

Some cause of dandruff.

1. Abnormal keratinization of the epidermal tissue.
2. Excess sebum (skin oil) secretion from skin.
3. Dry skin.
4. Insufficient/in appropriate cleaning of hair.
5. Scrubbing.
6. Fatigue.
7. Stress.

Types of Shampoo:-

- 1] Powder shampoo
- 2] Lotion shampoo
- 3] Cream shampoo
- 4] Baby shampoo
- 5] Conditioning shampoo
- 6] Anti-dandruff shampoo

Purpose:-

Reduce hair fall
Reduce dandruff
Promote shiny hair
Smoothing hair

Composition of General Shampoo:-^[19]**1] Surfactant:-**

Surfactants are the main component of shampoo. Mainly anionic surfactants are used. The raw material used in the manufacture of shampoo are:

Principal surfactants:

Provide detergency, foam and hair condition

Secondary surfactants: Improve detergency, foam and hair condition

Anionic surfactants: Are mostly used (good foaming properties).

The hydrophilic portion carries a negative charge which results in superior foaming, cleaning and end result attributes.

Non-ionic surfactants: Have good cleansing properties but do not have sufficient foaming powder.

Cationic surfactants: Are toxic and are hence not used however, they may be used in low concentration in hair conditioners.
Ampholytes: Being expensive, are generally not used. However, they are mainly used as secondary surfactants. And good hair conditioners.
 Example: Reetha and Shikakai.

2] Conditioning Agent:-

It is also called moisturizing in some cases and usually are composed of various oils and lubricant. One method of their use is coating of the substrate to alter their feel and appearance. Some materials use as conditioners in herbal shampoo.
 Example: Aloe vera herbal extracts.

3] Thickening Agent:-

These agents polymers that work by absorbing water to swell up and increase viscosity. Thickener used in herbal shampoo.
 Example: Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, Cetyl alcohol.

4] Color, Perfumes, Preservatives:-

Colouring agent are substances that is added to change formulation colour. Perfuming agent are the agent that is diffuses or impart agreeable or attractive Smell. Preservatives are the substances are added to prevent the formulation from microorganisms, undesirable chemical reactions. Example: propyl paraben, orange peel oil, Henna.

Material and Method:- Herbal Ingredients:-

1] Amla:-

Common name:- Indian gooseberry, Amla, Aamalaki, Aml.

Biological source:- This consists of dried, as well as fresh fruits of the plant *Emblica officinalis* Gaerth (*Phyllanthus emblica* Linn.), belongs to family:- Euphorbiaceae.

Geographical Source:- The plant is indigenous to India, although it can also be found growing in South East Asia, China, Malaysia, Pakistan, Uzbekistan, Sri Lanka and other tropical and subtropical countries.

Chemical constituents:- Amla consist Tannins, Alkaloids, Amino acid, Carbohydrates, Sterols, Triterpenes, Essential oils. Amla involve ellagic acid, Gallic acid, emblicanin A&B, phyllembein, guercetin, and ascorbic acid.

Uses:- Antidiabetics, Antimicrobial, Antioxidant, Antiemetic, Reducing dandruff, Improve in hair growth.

2] Neem:-

Common name:- Nimb, Kadu Limba, Nimba.

Biological source:- A fresh or dried leaves and seed oil of *Azadirachta indica* J. Juss (*Melia Indica* or *M. azadirachta* Linn.) belongs to family:- Meliaceae.

Geographical source:- It is found in India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Malaya, Indonesia, Japan, Tropical region of Australia and Africa. In India, it is found in Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Rajasthan, and M.P.

Chemical constituents:- Nimbin, 6- desacetylnimbinene. Nimbinene, Nimbandiol, nimbolide.

Uses:- Antimicrobial, Insect repellent, Insecticides, Antibacterial, Antidandruff.

3] Shikakai:-

Common name:- Soap-pod, Acacia concinna.

Biological source:- It is the dried gummy exudation of stem and branches of *Acacia Arabica* belonging to the family- Leguminosae.

Geographical source:- It is found in climbing shrub native to Asia, common in the warm plains of central and south India.

Chemical constituent:- It principally consists of arabin, which is a complex mixture of calcium, magnesium and potassium salts of Arabic acid.

Uses:- It is traditionally used in a shampoo preparation for hair growth, Soothes Scalp, Fights Dandruff, Nourishes hair follicles.

4] Reetha:-

Common name:- Wash nut, soap nut, soapberry,

Biological source:- It is dried fruit of plant *Sapindus mukorossi*. Belongs to Family:- Sapindaceae

Chemical constituent:- Reetha mainly contain saponins (10%-11.5). Sugar (10%) & mucilage. Triterpenes. Six sapindoside (sapindoside A, B, C, D, & mukorossisaponins (El & Y1)

Uses:- Used to shining hair, Used for curing hair issue, Natural Cleanser, Detergent foaming property.

5] Curry Leaves:-

Common name:- Surabhinimba, Mitha Neem, Kurry Patta, Kadhilimb.

Biological source:- It is a dried leaves of *Murrayakoenigii*. Belongs to family:- Rutaceae.

Chemical constituent:- The curry leaves are a rich source of many carbazole alkaloid with a diverse chemical composition. Leaves also contain terpenoids alkaloids such as cyclomahanimbine and Tetrahydromahanimbine the volatile oil that is present in fresh leaves is a rich source of vitamin A. Carbazole alkaloids are important such as girinimbine, murrayacine, koenioline,

Uses:- Curry leaves are used for treatment of anemia, diabetes, indigestion, obesity, kidney problems, hair and skin problems. Aiding digestion, promoting hair health, reducing cholesterol.

6] Bhringraj:-

Common name:-Bhringoraj, Falsedaisy.

Biological source:- It is a dried flower of *Eclipta alba (L.) Hassk.* (also known as *Ecliptaprostrata Roxb.*) belongs to the family:- Asteraceae.

Chemical constituent:- It consists of alkenynes, alkaloids, cardiac glycosides, flavonoids, lipids, steroids, saponins, steroid alkaloids, phytosterol, and triterpenes have been identified from the herb bhringraj.

Uses:- Its leaves are very effectively used as a liver cleanser and act as a hair tonic, Hair loss, Promotes hair growth.

7] AloeVera:-

Common name:- Chrits, Kumari & korphadmussblat

Biological source:-A juice of leaves of the *Aloe barbadensis Miller.* Belongs to family:- Liliacen

Chemical constituents:- It consists of Aloe-emodin, barbaloin, isobarbalom, beta- barbaloin, resins, alectic acid, homonataloin, aloe one chrysophanic acid, chrysaninimio acid, galachouronic acid, saponins.

Uses:- Purgative. Anti-inflammatory.

Treatment of burns & itching.

Extraction Process:- Maceration:-

- 1] Take all raw materials and make a powder with the help of a mortar and pestle. 2] Weigh all raw powder material about 40 grams.
- 3] Add all these raw powder materials to a specific iodine bottle.
- 4] Add ethanol into the iodine flask.
- 5] Make sure all raw materials are dipped into ethanol.
- 6] Fit the iodine bottle cap and cover the bottle with aluminum foil to avoid evaporation of ethanol and extract.
- 7] Keep aside the iodine bottle in a dark place at room temperature (28-30°C).
- 8] Put the iodine bottle aside for 7-8 days.
- 9] After 7-8 days filter the extract with filter paper in a beaker.
- 10] Removal of residue and collect the filtrate.
- 11] After collection of filtrate, evaporate the liquid with the help of a water bath.
- 12] Make sure the extract is fully dried and collected.

Preparation of herbal shampoo:-**Table no. 1:-Role of Ingredients.**

Sr. No.	Name of ingredients	Role of ingredients
1.	Amla	Strengthening of hair
2.	Neem	Anti dandruff agent
3.	Shikakai	To treat scalp disorder, Anti-inflammatory Agent
4.	Reetha	Natural foaming agent
5.	Curry leaves	Moisturize scalp (Anti-oxidant Agent)
6.	Bhringraj	Promote hair growth
7.	Aloevera	Nourishment to hair, anti septic
8.	Citric acid (lemon juice)	For pH adjuster
9.	Sodium lauryl sulphate	Foaming agent
10.	Cetyl alcohol	Thickening agent
11.	Rose water	Perfume
12.	Glycerin	Humectant
13.	0.1% Methyl parabensol ⁿ	Preservative
14.	Water	Vehicle

Procedure:-

1. Weigh all the herbal extracts given in the formula.
2. Take a beaker and add the cetyl alcohol in a beaker.
3. Take 20 ml of water in a measuring cylinder.
4. Add the water into another beaker, add cetyl alcohol slowly in water and boil it up to get fully dissolved.
5. Add the herbal ingredient to that beaker and continue to stir.
6. Add the SLS as surfactant in it.
7. Add a reetha as a foaming agent in it.
8. Add aloevera as a moisturizing agent in it.
9. Add a few drops of citric acid as a PH adjuster.
10. Add the Solution A 0.05% methyl paraben for preservation.
11. Then finally add water up to 100 ml.
12. Shampoo has been prepared.
13. Perform the evaluation parameters.

Formulation:-

F1:- For100 ml Shampoo.

Tableno.2:-F1 Formulation (In this formulation thickness of shampoo is increases, decrease the concentration of cetyl alcohol.)

Sr. No.	NameofIngredients	Quantity
1.	Amla	0.60 mg
2.	Neem	0.50 mg
3.	Shikakai	0.55 mg
4.	Reetha	7 gm
5.	Curry leaves	0.59 mg
6.	Bhringraj	0.53 mg
7.	Aloevera	5 ml
8.	Citricacid(lemon juice)	q.s.
9.	Sodiumlaurylsulphate	5 gm
10.	Cetylalcohol	12 gm
11.	Rosewater	q.s.
12.	Glycerin	3 ml
13.	0.1%Methylparabensolution	2 ml
14.	Water	Upto 100 ml

F2:- For100 mlShampoo.

Tableno.3:-F2 formulation (In this formulation foaming of shampoo is less, increase the concentration of reetha.)

Sr. No.	Name of Ingredients	Quantity
1.	Amla	0.60 mg
2.	Neem	0.50 mg
3.	Shikakai	0.55 mg
4.	Reetha	7 gm
5.	Curry leaves	0.59 mg
6.	Bhringraj	0.53 mg
7.	Aloevera	5 ml
8.	Citricacid(lemon juice)	q.s.
9.	Sodiumlaurylsulphate	5 gm
10.	Cetylalcohol	9 gm
11.	Rosewater	q.s.
12.	Glycerin	3 ml
13.	0.1%Methylparabensolution	2 ml
14.	Water	Upto 100 ml

F3:- For100 mlShampoo.

Tableno.4:-F3 Formulation (In this formulation foaming and viscosity is good.)

Sr. No.	Name of Ingredients	Quantity
1.	Amla	0.60 mg
2.	Neem	0.50 mg
3.	Shikakai	0.55 mg
4.	Reetha	9 gm
5.	Curry leaves	0.59 mg
6.	Bhringraj	0.53 mg
7.	Aloevera	5 ml
8.	Citricacid(lemon juice)	q.s.
9.	Sodiumlaurylsulphate	7 gm
10.	Cetylalcohol	9 gm
11.	Rosewater	q.s.
12.	Glycerin	3 ml
13.	0.1%Methylparabensolution	2 ml
14.	Water	Upto 100 ml

Evaluation Parameters:-

The three formulations were evaluated by following parameters

1] Physical appearance:-^[20]

The formulation prepared were evaluated in terms of their colour, odour, appearance, transparency, consistency.

2] Dirt dispersion:-^[21]

Two drops of shampoo were added in a large test tube contain 10ml of distilled water. 1 ml of India ink was added; the test was stoppered and shaken as 10 times. The amount of ink in the foam was estimated as None, Light, Moderate or Heavy.

3] Foam ability and foam stability:-^[22]

Foaming ability was determine by using cylinder shake method. Briefly, 50 ml of the herbal shampoo solution was placed into a 250ml graduated cylinder. It was covered with one hand & shaken 10 times. The total volume of foam content after 1 minutes of shaking was recorded.

Foam stability was evaluated by recording the foam volume after 1 min & 4 min of shake test.

4] Wetting time test:-

A canvas paper was cut into 1 inch diameter disc having an average weight of 0.449. The smooth surface of disc was placed on the surface of herbal shampoo solution the stopwatch started. The time required for the disc to begin to sink was noted down as the wetting time.

5] Determination of pH:-

Firstly calibrate pH meter by using 07 pH buffer medium and mix 01 gm of shampoo with 09 ml of water and determine the pH using pH meter at 27°C.

6] Detergency and cleansing action:-

1. Cleansing power is evaluated by the method of 5gm sample of soiled human hair is placed at 35°C & 200 cc of water containing of 1 gm of shampoo.

2. The flask is shaken 50 times a minute for 4 minutes. Then washed once again with sufficient amount of water, then after filter the hair dried & weighed.

3. The amount of soil is removed under these condition is calculated.

7] Consistency:-

1. The consistency of the shampoo was determined by hand.

2. Take a pinch of shampoo and rub it with your hand.

8] Irritation and sensitivity test:-

Irritation and sensitivity test of shampoo was determined by applying the 1 gm of shampoo in the hand for 2 minutes and the result is noted down.

9] Determination percent solid contain:-^[21]

A clean, dry evaporating dish was weighed and added 4 gram's of herbal shampoo to the evaporating dish. The exact weight of the shampoo was calculated only and put the evaporating dish with shampoo was placed on the hot plate until the liquid portion was evaporated. The weight of the shampoo only (solids) after drying was calculated.

Results**Physical appearance:-****Table no. 5:- Physical appearance.**

Sr.No.	Properties	F1	F2	F3
1.	Color	Brownish	Brownish	Brownish
2.	Odour	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant
3.	Appearance	Semisolid	Semisolid	Semisolid
4.	Transparency	Nontransparent	Nontransparent	Nontransparent
5.	Consistency	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth

Dirt dispersion:-**Table no. 6:- Dirt dispersion.**

Formulation	F1	F2	F3
Result	Light	Light	Moderate

Foam ability and foam stability:-**Table no.7:- Foam ability and foam stability.**

Formulation	F1	F2	F3
Foam volume (ml)	110	130	170

Wetting time test:-**Table no.8:-Wetting time test.**

Formulation	F1	F2	F3
Time	50 second	42 second	35 second

Determination of pH:-**Table no.9:-Determination of pH.**

Formulation	F1	F2	F3
pH1	6.28	7.00	6.29
pH2	6.48	6.69	7.00
pH3	6.29	6.28	6.75

Detergency and cleansing action:-**Table no.10:-Detergency and cleansing action.**

Formulation	F1	F2	F3
Result	Good	Average	Good

Consistency:-**Table no. 11:- Consistency.**

Formulation	F1	F2	F3
Consistency	Good	Good	Good

Irritation and sensitivity test:-**Table no.12:-Irritation and sensitivity test.**

Formulation	F1	F2	F3
Result	Noirritation	Noirritation	Noirritation

Determination percent solid contain:-**Table no.13:-Determination percent solid contain.**

Formulation	F1	F2	F3
Result	1.2 gm	1.00 gm	0.9 gm

CONCLUSION

The herbal liquid shampoo was formulated by using the various herbal ingredients. From the overall results, we can conclude that the herbal shampoo formulation 3 (F3) was more stable as compared to other formulation on the basis of their evaluation parameters.

It was found to be harmless, more effective and economical.

The future advantage of herbal shampoo is having less or no side effect and will provide good hair growth in less time and reduce the risk of dandruff.

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